

The Impact of Parental Support and Interest Learning for the Result of Grade VIII SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Year 2023/2024

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A R Q I C L E I N F O

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Parental support, Interest learning, Study for result

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This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach with the testing media used is SPSS 21. The population in this study was 277 people, and the sample used was 163 people. The sample collection technique used was Proportionate Stratified Random sampling. The data collection technique used was a questionnaire. The hypothesis data collection technique uses multiple regression analysis and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results of this study state that: 1) there is a positive influence of learning achievement on learning discipline. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of parental support ($5.657 > t$ table value 1.65437). 2) there is a positive influence of interest in learning on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value of interest in learning ($5.689 > t$ table value 1.65437) which means this variable is significant. 3) parental support and interest in learning together influence learning achievement. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value ($1441.624 > F$ table value 3.05). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.947, which means that 94.7% of the variables are the influence of parental support and interest in learning on the learning achievement of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar and 6.3% is the influence of other variables that were not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

Education is important for human survival. Education is an activity carried out by every human being so that they obtain knowledge that can be developed as a preparation to become a qualified and responsible successor to the nation, especially in the development of science and technology. According to Winkel in Susanti Lidia (2019:33) learning achievement is evidence of learning success or a student's ability to carry out learning activities according to the weight he has achieved. Learning achievement is the extent to which students are measured after following the learning process in a certain period which can be measured using relevant instruments. From this explanation, learning achievement consists of two, namely achievement and learning.

Parental support is a person's perception that he is part of a social network in which each member supports each other. Social support is a form of providing a sense of comfort, both physically and psychologically, by the family. Parents play an important role in children's learning stages, namely in the form of support. Parental attention can provide encouragement and motivation so that children can study diligently, because children need time, place and good conditions to learn. With support from parents, students can be more confident in starting learning at school, so that when the learning process takes place in class, students can follow the direction of teaching and learning activities in class. From the above understanding, this is in contrast to the conditions encountered by researchers when they were at the Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Middle School where students were still found who did not do the assignments given by the teacher for various reasons, namely the lack of study time given by their parents because they had less time at home. more to help parents than learning, many of their stationery are also incomplete so in this case it can disrupt the learning process in the classroom. Apart from support from parents, interest in learning is also the cause of low student achievement. Because interest is a concentration of attention that contains elements of feelings, pleasure, inclinations, involuntary desires that are active in nature to receive something from outside (the environment). Interest can be understood as an ability that exists in every human being, namely attention, a person's inclination towards something. So interest can determine the attitude that causes someone to be active in a job. Someone who has an interest in learning means that someone has a passion for learning so that it influences the student's learning achievement. Interest in learning is an interest in a lesson being studied, which then encourages students to study and pursue that lesson. Apart from parental support, interest in learning is also necessary to improve student learning achievement.

If the result is that there is no interest or encouragement from within oneself to learn then support from parents will be in vain, but if student interest in learning is high then it will improve learning outcomes. student. Likewise, student interest in learning at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar is still very low because there are still students who are noisy or chat with their classmates when the teacher explains the material in front, students who fall asleep during the learning process in class, students who excuse themselves. to the bathroom, some students even left while the lesson was going on. Things like this are what cause the learning achievement of students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar to decline. Based on the above phenomenon, the author is interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Parental Support and Interest in Learning on the Learning Achievement of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Academic Year 2023/2024".

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In which each member supports each other Based on the explanation above, the author agrees with Lestari (2022:60) "Parental support is a form of assistance given by parents to their children which aims to help children so that they feel more comfortable, less stressed and act as a source of motivation for children in facing and solve the problems they face.

According to Slameto in Then, W (2020:3), "Interest in learning is a feeling of liking or being interested in something or a learning activity without anyone telling you to". Then according to Renninger, Hidi & Krapp in Then, W (2017:3), "interest in learning is a phenomenon that arises from individual interactions with their environment". Interest in learning is a tendency to pay attention and act towards people, activities or situations that are the object of that interest accompanied by feelings of pleasure.

METHODS

This research was conducted at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar Jl Sibolga No.25, kec. South Siantar, Pematang Siantar City, North Sumatra. This research uses a quantitative approach with survey methods. The population of this study were Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. The sampling technique used in this research was proportionate random sampling, so the number of samples used by researchers was 163 people. The data collected in this research is the result of distributing questionnaires through questionnaires and then to determine whether the instrument statement items are suitable to be given, the validity of the instrument is first carried out. The validity test was tested using SPSS 21, the reliability used the Cronbach Alpha formula. The test results that have been tested are then given to the sample. The data analysis technique used to test the research hypothesis is the T test and F test. Before carrying out the t test, the prerequisite tests are first carried out, namely the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test.

According to Susanti Lidia (2019:33) learning achievement is proof of a student's success or ability to carry out their learning activities according to the weight they have achieved. Susanti Lidia (2019:30) revealed that learning achievement is expressed in the form of symbols, numbers, letters and sentences which can reflect the results that have been achieved by each student in a certain period and it can be said that learning achievement is the result of a learning activity accompanied by changes achieved by students.

Based on the explanation above, Susanti Lidia (2019:9) agrees that learning achievement is expressed in the form of symbols, numbers, letters and sentences which can reflect the results achieved by each student in a certain period and it can be said that learning achievement is the results of a learning activity accompanied by changes achieved by students.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Before testing the hypothesis, prerequisite tests are carried out, namely the normality test, multicollinearity test and heteroscedasticity test. Based on the normality test, it is presented in the following table:

Table 1. Normality Test Results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		163
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	,0000000
	Std. Deviation	6,92008577
	Absolute Most Extreme Differences	,042
	Positive	,042
	Negative	-,042
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,541
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,932

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

Based on the results of the normality test, it is known that the significance value is $0.932 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed.

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Dukungan Orang 1 Tua	,044	22,649
Minat belajar	,044	22,649

a. Dependent Variable: Learning achievement

It can be seen from the table above that the tolerance value for the independent variable is 0.44 and the VIF value for the independent variable is 22,649 based on the tolerance value of $0.44 > 0.10$, so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity of the independent variables and the VIF value is $22,649 > 10.00$, meaning there is multicollinearity between the independents.

Table 3. T Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	7,584	1,204		6,301	,000
X1	,469	,083	,488	5,657	,000
X2	,485	,085	,491	5,689	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning achievement

Based on table 4.7, it is known that the constant value (a) is 7.584, while the value of parental support (b1) is 0.469 and the value of interest in learning (b2) is 0.485.

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	13088,770	2	6544,385	1441,624	,000 ^b
Residual	726,334	160	4,540		
Total	13815,104	162			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Interest in Learning, Parental Support

Based on table 4.9, it is found that the Fcount value (1441.624) is greater than the Ftable value (3.05). This indicates that the research results reject H0 and accept H1. Thus, together parental support and interest in learning influence the student achievement variable at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar with a significant level of influence. This means that the hypothesis which states that parental support and interest in learning jointly influence student learning achievement variables at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar can be accepted.

In the classical assumption results, the normality test is the main requirement to be able to proceed to the multiple regression test stage with the data having a normal distribution and a significance level > 0.05 . The variables of parental support, interest in learning and student achievement have a normal distribution between variables with a significance level of $0.200 > 0.05$. and based on Figure 4.2, the p-plot curve can be seen that the distribution of data is on a diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal, so that the values are standardized and follow the assumption of normality.

The results of the multi collinearity test show that the tolerance is > 0.10 , and the variance inflation factor (VIP) is $22,649 > 10$ and the tolerance value is $0.44 > 0.10$, so it can be concluded that the data has symptoms of multi collinearity. The results of the heteroscedasticity test in Figure 4.1 show that the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis. Thus it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity, and based on table 4.8 it is known that the significant value of parental support is (0.7,584) and the significant value of interest in learning (0.485 and parental support value (0.469) can be concluded that there are symptoms of heteroskedasticity because the significance value must be greater than 0.05. Based on table 4.10, it is known that the constant value (a) is 7.584, while the value of parental support (b) is 0.469 and the value of interest in learning (2) is 0.485, so the regression equation is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 7.584 + 0.469 X_1 + 0.485 X_2 + 726.334$$

A constant of 7.584 means that the consistent value of the learning achievement variable is 7.584. The regression coefficient X1 is 0.469 and X2 is 0.0485. The regression coefficient is positive, so it can be said that the direction of influence of variables X1 and Variable X2 on Y is positive. The t test results are based on table 4. The calculated t value of parental support (5.657) is greater than the t table (1.65437). Based on the results obtained, H1 is rejected and H0 is accepted for the parental support variable. Thus, parental support influences learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. and the calculated t value of interest in learning (5.689) is greater than the t table (1.65437). Based on the results obtained, H0 is rejected and H1 is accepted for the learning interest variable. Thus, parental support partially influences learning achievement, and interest in learning partially influences study achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. Personally, the variable interest in learning has a more dominant influence than parental support style.

This can be seen from parental support having the highest value (5.689), meaning that the parental support variable has more influence in improving learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. The F test results based on table 4.9 show that the Fcount value (1441.624) is greater than the Ftable value (3.05). This identifies that the research results reject H_0 and accept H_1 . Thus, together parental support and interest in learning influence the learning achievement variables of students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. With a significant level of influence. The value of the coefficient of determination R square in table 4.10 is known to be 0.947, which means that 94.7% of the variable is parental support and influences the learning achievement of students at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar, while 6.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of parental support on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of parental support (5.657) < t table value (1.65437) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of interest in learning on learning achievement. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of interest in learning (5.689) > t table (1.65437) which means this variable is significant. Parental support and interest in learning together influence learning achievement. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (1441.624) > Ftable value (3.05). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.947, which means that 94.7% of the variables of parental support and interest in learning influence student learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 6.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

Suggestion

1. Parental support and interest in learning have a positive and significant effect on learning achievement at SMP Negeri 12 Pematang Siantar. Therefore, to improve student learning achievement, you should pay attention to these two factors so that learning achievement at school increases. support from parents who are like parents who pay more attention to how their children learn, parents who pay attention to their children's development and provide equipment. Interest in learning also greatly influences student learning achievement in schools. With high interest in learning, activities in the learning process in class run well
2. For future researchers to use other variables that influence student learning achievement. If in the future someone does similar research, they should do it in a different place, add the research variables and adjust the time to the period of the research being carried out.

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